

Improving the Thermal Sustainability of Modern Gas Turbine Blade using Newly Proposed Coolant Passage Shapes

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Abstract - In order to enhance the turbine efficiency and power, modern Gas turbine engine are required to operate at higher Temperature. Because of this, the turbine components are experiencing the increasing heat loads. The blades from the gas turbines are getting damaged due to the creep, fatigue, thermal stress etc., and it is reduced by applying the external and internal coolant inside the blades. The external cooling process possesses less heat convection rate when compared to internal one. The internal open loop cooling has coolant wastages and corrosion on the surface. But in the internal closed loop cooling the coolant can be reusable and reduce fatigue fracture formation at the surface. The Internal Closed Loop Cooling depends on the shape and size of coolant passages and types of the coolant used. In this paper, newly designed coolant passage shapes such as four star tip (4ST), four star smooth (4SS), five star tip (5ST), five star smooth (5SS), hexagon tip (HT), hexagon smooth (HS) for the future gas turbine are proposed.

Keywords: coolant passage shapes, internal closed loop cooling, gas turbine blade, 4ST, 4SS, 5ST, 5SS, HT, HS.

I. INTRODUCTION

To improve the efficiency and the specific thrust of modern gas turbine engines cooled turbine blade has been widely used. Efficient cooling techniques are often used to enable the blade material to sustain the high Temperature.

a) Environment and failure modes

^[1]Turbine blades are subjected to very strenuous environments inside a gas turbine. They face high temperatures, high stresses, and a potentially high vibration environment. All three of these factors can lead to blade failures, which can destroy the engine, and turbine blades are carefully designed to resist those conditions.

^[1]The first stage (the stage directly following the combustor) of a modern turbine faces temperatures around 2,500 ° F (1,370 ° C), up from temperatures around 1,500 ° F (820 ° C) in early gas turbines. Modern military jet engines, like the Snecma M88, can see turbine temperatures of 2,900 ° F (1,590 ° C). Those high temperatures weaken the blades and make them more susceptible to creep failures. The high temperatures can also make the blades susceptible to corrosion failures. Finally, vibrations from the engine and the turbine itself can cause fatigue failures.

b) Reduction of blade failure

The reduction of blade failure was carried out by three ways.

They are

- By Using high temperature super alloys
- By Providing coatings over the super alloys
- By making coolant passages (new shapes)

Fig (1) Modern gas turbine engine & engine blade & coolant passage

c) Need of new coolant passage shapes

^[3]Gas turbines are used extensively for aircraft propulsion, land-based power generation, and industrial applications. Developments in turbine cooling technology play a critical role in increasing the thermal efficiency and power output of advanced gas turbines. The current coolant passages and coolants are providing less heat convection efficiency and more frictional effect. So it is essential to identify new coolant passage shape & new coolant to overcome the current problem.

II. CONCEPT GENERATION

a) Heat Convection

Transfer of heat from one medium (blade) to another medium (coolant) is called convective heat transfer. If the heat transfer is done by an external force means that is called forced convection the heat convection amount is depends on the area contact between blade and coolant, material properties, coolant properties, and coolant passage shape. - *Newton's law of cooling*

If the Amount of Curvature present in the contact area is more, then the Heat convection between the solid and liquid is more. - *Heat Transfer Handbook*

b) Blade Life

For every turbine blade, there should be a definite life time. Because of some environmental and external factors (like temperature), the life of the blade tends to reduced. The cooling techniques (my design) used to retain the blade life and also increase the withstanding capacity of the blade. - *Fatigue life prediction theory*

III. PROPOSED SHAPES

- Four star tip(4ST)
- Four star smooth(4SS)
- Five star tip(5ST)
- Five star smooth(5SS)

- Hexagon tip(HT)
- Hexagon smooth(HS)

a) CAD models (2D)

(a) Four star tip (4ST)

(b) Four star smooth

(c) Five star tip (5ST)

(d) Five star smooth (5SS)

(E) Hexagon Tip (HT)

(f) Hexagon smooth (HS)

b) Shape Optimization

This paper explains about the shape optimization of coolant passage and the need of coolant for the turbine. The calculation for requirement of the coolant and coolant factor, thermal analysis thermal analysis should be done. Here the simple thermal equilibrium equations are done for the evaluations and analysis of optimized turbine blade. The steam is used as coolant and hot turbine inlet gas is air.

Table1. Different area of the coolant passage

S no	Name of the profile	Area(mm ²)
1	4 tip smooth star	135
2	4 tip star	137.7639
3	5 tip smooth star	149.5
4	5 tip star	154.1125
5	Hexagon tip	184.620
6	Hexagon smooth	182.50

The inlet temperature of the coolant is assumed to be 30 °C as liquid and it is converting as steam after entering the initial stage of the turbine blade. The blade temperature is maintained as 1100 °C and the temperature of inlet gas is varied. The coolant passage for turbine shape is optimized as four design aspects as shown the fig.1, and the respective area is shown in the Table. (i). the span of the aerofoil is 160mm and chord is 49.5mm. The constant outer diameter is maintained and internal shape of the turbine blade is modified. There are two type's coolant passage shapes that are four stars and five star shapes, again optimization in tip of the coolant passage.

The thermodynamic equilibrium is solved and the turbine inlet gas $m_g C_p \Delta T$ is equal to the coolant heat of $m_c C_p \Delta T$. By solving the equ.1., the exit gas temperature is obtained and given the literature[6]. Here the effectiveness is assumed as 0.21-0.25 and the equation is used to find the unknown parameter of turbine exit temperature. The coolant factor and coolant ratio equation is directly taken from the literature[5],[6]

$$m_g C_{pg} (T_{gi} - T_{ge}) = m_c C_{pc} (T_{ce} - T_{ci}) \quad (1)$$

$$T_{ge} = T_{gi} - \left\{ S_{tg} - \left(\frac{A_b}{A_g} \right) (T_g - T_b) \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$T_{ce} = \epsilon (T_b - T_{ci}) + T_{ci} \quad (3)$$

$$\left(\frac{m_c}{m_g} \right) = \left(\frac{C_{pg}}{C_{pc}} \right) \cdot S_{tg} \cdot \left(\frac{A_b}{A_g} \right) \cdot \frac{1}{\epsilon} \cdot \left\{ \frac{T_g - T_b}{T_b - T_c} \right\} \quad (4)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The equation is mathematically solved and analyzed in MATLAB. The turbine gas inlet temperature is varied from 1200 °C to 2000 °C by maintained the blade temperature as 1100 °C. The variation of coolant mass ratio is determined by varying the turbine inlet temperature and effectiveness as shown in the Fig.2. For the effectiveness of 0.21 the coolant mass ration is given as 2.35E-04 and for effectiveness of 0.25 is given as 2.05E-04 at constant gas inlet temperature of 1500 °C. The gas inlet temperature to the exit is decrease when the coolant is passed to maintain the blade temperature.

But the efficiency of the turbine is decreasing when the gas moves to the next stage of the turbine. But in this proposed design the exit gas temperature is approximately equal to the inlet gas temperature. The coolant temperature is increased up to 265.4 °C and maintained the blade temperature constant. Fig.3. shows the variation of coolant factor at various temperatures for different shapes of turbine coolant passage. The coolant factor is increased when contact surface area of the coolant to the blade is increased. The coolant passage is designed as triangle in shape and angle is less for 5ST compared to 4ST and it acts as fin.

Fig.2. Analysis of coolant mass flow rate at various temperatures

Fig.3. Analysis of coolant factor at various temperatures

The coolant is passing through all the passage at different areas from leading edge to trailing edge. This maintain the blade temperature as constant at all the area of the turbine blade and increases the coolant factor. The smooth surface also plays a role in coolant factor but less compared tip shapes. The

smooth of the coolant passage is very useful when moving to high thermal stress.

V. CONCLUSION

The analyses for coolant factor and coolant mass flow rates are done for various shapes of turbine blade coolant passage at various parameters. The five star tips like structure shows maximum coolant factor of 0.0168 at 1500°C as compared to all other shapes, because of high contact surface area. The closed loop cooling helps for additional usage of steam for external purposes like refrigeration. The exit temperature of coolant is increased up to 265.4 °C at $\epsilon = 0.21$. The coolant passage at different places like leading and trailing edge helps to maintain the blade temperature as constant.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Kyung Min Kim, Jun Su Park, Dong Hyun Lee, Tack Woon Lee, Hyung Hee Cho, Analysis of Conjugated Heat transfer, stress and failure in a gas turbine blade with circular cooling passages, *Engineering Failure Analysis* 18, 2011, 1212–1222.
- [2] Carlo Carcasci, Bruno Facchini, A numerical procedure to design internal cooling of gas turbine stator blade, Elsevier, Paris, *Rev Gen Therm* 35, 1996, 257-268
- [3] Giovanni Cerri, Ambra Giovannelli, Lorenzo Battisti, Roberto Fedrizzi, Advances in effusive cooling techniques of gas turbines, *Applied Thermal Engineering* 27, 2007, 692–698
- [4] Mohamed G. Ghorab, Adiabatic and conjugate cooling effectiveness analysis of a new hybrid scheme, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences* 50, 2011, 965-983.
- [5] Sanjay, Onkar Singh, B.N. Prasad, Influence of different means of turbine blade cooling on the thermodynamic performance of combined cycle *Applied Thermal Engineering* 28, 2008,2315–2326,
- [6] Daniele Fiaschi, Giampaolo Manfrida, Philippe Mathieu, Duccio Tempesti, Performance of an oxy-fuel Combustion CO₂ power cycle including blade cooling, *Energy* 34, 2009, 2240–2247
- [7] W. D. Morris and S. W. Chang, An experimental study of heat transfer in a simulated turbine blade cooling passage, *Int. J. Heat and Mass Transfer*. 1997, Vol. 40, No. 15, pp. 3703-3716.
- [8] Bruno Facchini, Blade cooling improvement for heavy duty gas turbine: The air coolant Temperature Reduction and the introduction of steam and mixed steam air Cooling, *Int. J. Therm. Sci.*2000,39, 74–84
- [9] Noot and marc johnannes, Numerical analysis of turbine blade cooling ducts, ISBN 90- 1997, 386- 0581-1
- [10] Dong-Ho Rhee, Hyung Hee Cho, Effect of vane/blade relative position on heat Transfer characteristics in a stationary turbine blade, Part 1. Tip and shroud, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences* 47, 2008, 1528–1543,
- [11] Dong-Ho Rhee and Hyung Hee Cho, Effect of vane/blade relative position on heat Transfer characteristics in a stationary turbine blade: Part 2. Blade surface, *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*,47, 2008,1544–1554,
- [12] Han, Je-Chin and Lesley M. Wright. Enhanced Internal Cooling of Turbine Blades and Vanes. *The gas Turbine Handbook*. 2006. 26 Nov